

wing figure are obtained according as we are dealing with the modification which is stable, or with that which is metastable below 39°.

As is to be foreseen, the velocity of reaction at 39° is the same in both cases; below this temperature the reaction in the element containing the stable phase is always the faster (at the same temperature).

Phys. — “*Diffraction of RÖNTGEN Rays*”. By Prof. H. HAGA and Dr. C. H. WIND.

Investigations¹⁾ formerly undertaken in the Groningen Laboratory rendered it already clear that, if X rays are due to vibrations of the ether, their wavelength can be but a few ANGSTROM units. In the course of the further enquiry a phenomenon was observed, indicating traces of real diffraction and tending to give a wavelength of one or two ANGSTROM units. Now it became possible to perform a new series of experiments under circumstances more qualified to exhibit diffraction. A simple consideration makes it clear that in order to obtain great intensity it is better to use narrow slits than to make the distances great.

¹⁾ C. H. WIND, “On the influence of the dimensions of the source of light in diffraction phenomena of FRESNEL and on the diffraction of X rays”. Kon. Akad. van Wetenschappen. Proceedings, June 1898.

All the apparatus could now be mounted on one plate of free-stone, whereby moreover greater steadiness was secured.

The first slit (X slit), the second (diffraction slit) and the photographic plate were mounted on heavy metallic stands, resting on a free-stone plate ($200 \times 40 \times 30$ cm.) This plate was supported by three columns of the same material, resting on the great pillar of the edifice; stands, plate, column and pillar were united by plaster of Paris.

Behind the first slit was the RÖNTGEN tube, one of the excellent tubes made by MÜLLER (Hamburg) with automatic vacuum regulator.

The induction coil was an excellent piece of apparatus made by SIEMENS and HALSKE, with a maximum spark-length of 30 cm. and a DEPRez interruptor with two contacts.

The current for the induction coil was given by 6 accumulators. The tube and the first slit were surrounded at all sides — except at the backside, where space was kept for the connecting wires between the coil and the tube — with thick leaden plates; in the direction of the diffraction slit a small aperture was spared in order to enable the X rays to reach the photographic plate. Much pain has been taken to obtain the slits as excellent as possible; the small platinum plates, thick $\frac{1}{2}$ mm., which formed the edges of the slit, had been very carefully flattened and ground and were screwed on flattened plates of brass. The width of the X slit was 14, 18 or 25 microns; by means of a leaden plate the height was limited to 1 cm.

The diffraction slit (height 3 cm.) was 14 microns at the upper end and gradually narrowing to a width of a few microns.

On one of the sides of the diffraction slit and very near to it there had been drilled small round holes in the platinum, near to the upper and lower end and to the centre of the slit, in order to enable us, in a way afterwards to be mentioned, to know the effective width of each part of the diffraction slit. The diffraction slit ended at the top and at the bottom in a slit of considerable width (3 m.m), the axis of which was the prolongation of the axis of the diffraction slit; the RÖNTGEN tube was placed behind the first slit in such a position that these wider slits cut from the pencil of X rays the most intensive, middle part, as could easily be controlled, from time to time, by means of a fluorescent screen; of course the rays then passed also in the desired manner by the diffraction slit.

With this arrangement were taken the experiments of which the results are given in the following table, where signifies

- σ : width of the first slit in microns.
 s : " " " diffraction slit " "
 a : distance between first and diffraction slit in cm.
 b : " " diffraction slit and photographic plate in cm.

$$a = 75 \text{ cm.} \quad s : 2 \text{ à } 14 \mu.$$

σ	b	Time of exposition Hours.	N ^o . of experiment.
25	1	29	5
25	20	57	3
25	45	66	4
14	75	60	1
14	75	100	2
25	105,5	150	6
18	1	30	8
18	75	130	7
18	75	200	9

In the experiment N^o. 1 a plate sensitive on both sides was used — mark B II of the Actien-Gesellschaft für Anilin-Fabrikation. The image on the second side of the plate however was many times fainter than that on the first side; moreover on account of the rather strong fog it seemed very desirable to destroy the image on the second side and to remove the gelatine film; in the other experiments LOMBERG-plates were used. The plates were developed a very long time (at least half an hour) using rodinal (1 at 35), potassium bromide being added.

In experiments 5 and 8, the photographic plate was pressed against the brass plate, on which the diffraction slit was mounted. Measurements, in order to give the width of the slit, were made on the images obtained by these experiments, greater accuracy being attainable in this manner than by direct measurement of the slit; on account of the small distance between the plate and the slit, the image could not be sensibly broadened nor by diffraction nor by the X slit being

THE DIFFRACTION OF THE RÖNTGEN-RAYS.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

not infinitely narrow. The measurements were made by means of a microscope made by ZEISS, object-glass D, compensation eye-piece 6 with micrometer; also low powers were used.

The above mentioned small holes in one of the slit sides gave on **5** and **8** circular and on the other plates — on account of the height of the X ray source — elongated dark images (cf. fig. 1 and 2). On all plates the distances between the centres of these images were divided with the dividing engine in the same number of equal parts. Whenever for a definite division in one of the diffraction images the corresponding width of the diffraction slit was wanted, we could by this way immediately take it from the measurements of **5** and **8**.

If, using small power — object-glass a*, index at 10, compensation eye-glass 6 — plate N^o. **2** is gradually displaced, one sees that the image of the slit appears in the broader part as a black line, dark in the centre and with hazy edges, that however in the narrower part the darker part — nucleus — ceases and the image of the slit broadens out somewhat like a plume, showing but little difference of intensity in a direction perpendicular to the length of the image. In accordance with the gradual narrowing of the diffraction slit, the image becomes of course weaker, but narrower alone at a few places, in such a manner that from the point, where the nucleus seems to disappear, maxima and minima begin to appear in the width of the image.

The same thing occurs also in the other negatives, most clearly in N^o. **2**, **6** and **9**.

In order to give some idea of the character of these faint broadenings, which are observed at their best with the microscope, we have made of the narrowest part of **5** and **2** enlarged photographs by means of a so called mikroplanar N^o. I_a made by ZEISS. Figures 1 and 2 are reproductions of these enlargements by means of heliography.

Fig. 1 is enlarged 16 times, fig. 2 14 times.

Identical numbers at the divisions indicate corresponding places. In fig. 1 is given also the width of the diffraction slit.

In order to be sure that the real cause of the described phenomena is to be attributed to diffraction, we have carefully considered other different causes which might cause a broadening of the image of the slit. It appeared however, that though photographic irradiation, local differences in the sensibility of the photographic film, secondary rays (SAGNAC), small motions of the stands during the experiments, often extending over more than 10 days, may have changed in different degrees the image of the slit, these causes

cannot explain the broadenings of the image, which as we observed occur with the narrowing of the diffraction slit.

It might however be argued that if the influence of the width of the first slit is taken into account, also with linear propagation of the rays, the image of the slit *might* make upon us the impression of a broadening with the gradually narrowing of the second slit. In this case however the apparent limits of the image should *at the utmost* diverge at the same rate as the edges of the second slit approach each other. In our experiments however the diffraction slit narrows in so slow a manner that a broadening from *this* cause would be totally imperceptible.

Hence we can only draw the conclusion, that the broadenings of the slit image we have observed must be attributed to a **Diffraction of the Röntgen rays**. With this hypothesis the different broadenings of the slit image, which are to be interpreted as manifold formations of plumes, are easily explained, because it is only necessary to suppose that there are rays of considerably different wavelengths, rays of some definite wavelengths possessing greater energy than others; the rays with great energy cause the separate broadenings resembling plumes, the height of the ray source favouring haziness.

The small intensity of the broadenings resembling plumes, the haziness of their edges make accurate measurements and hence a precise determination of the wavelength impossible. We were obliged to make only an estimation of the wavelength of the more prominent rays.

In FRESNEL's diffraction theory is introduced the quantity v ; in conformity therewith we now introduce the quantity v_s , as given by the relation

$$v_s = s \sqrt{\frac{2(a+b)}{ab\lambda}}.$$

This quantity determines, s , a , b and λ being given, the kind of the primary diffraction image to be expected, so that by means of CORNU's spiral the intensity curve of the diffraction image can be constructed. We have done so for the values 2, 1.5 and 1 of the quantity v_s . The width of the first slit, σ , must however be taken into account, or which comes to the same thing, from the primary the secondary diffraction images must be deduced. ¹⁾

¹⁾ C. H. WIND, „Over den invloed van de afmetingen der lichtbron bij FRESNEL'sche buigingsverschijnselen”. Verslag der vergad. April 1897.

In order to obtain a somewhat general survey of the different possible cases, which were for us of importance, we have made concerning the ratio

$$\delta = \frac{\frac{b}{a} \sigma}{a \pm b} s$$

the significance of which will be clear, three hypotheses, viz. $\delta=3$, $\delta=1$ and $\delta=0,6$.

The first slit is with the first hypothesis rather wide, with the third rather narrow as compared with the second slit. The intensity curves for the diffraction images in the 9 cases are plotted down in fig. 3 a—i.

In the same plate are represented also by dotted lines the intensity curves with the same slits and with rectilinear propagation, using the circumstance that the areas enclosed between the intensity curves and the axis must be the same with and without diffraction.

From these figures it appears that already with great values of v_s broadening will be visible, provided that the least perceptible intensity, is *very* small as compared with the greatest intensity, which with given width occurs in the image of the slit.

However in our case of the broadenings resembling plumes the last condition is certainly not fulfilled; in the centre of the slit image the intensity is already small, and a high ratio at the edges would be necessary in order to be perceptible.

In this case we see at once from the curves, that with a value $v_s=1$ there must be in *all* cases a distinct broadening, with $v_s=2$ probably never, with $v_s=1,5$ only under favourable circumstances as to the width of the first slit, and then only in a small degree.

It is also clear that, though the influence of the value of δ on the visibility of a broadening exists in general, yet this influence is not great for values of v_s between 1 and 1,5. Taking this into account we think to be justified to take $v_s=1,3$ in every case the slit image is sensibly broadened, that is in the case of every plume.

Hence we find by means of the relation

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{1,3^2} \frac{2(a+b)}{ab} s_1^2,$$

where s_1 is the width of the diffraction slit corresponding with a broadening, the values in the following table :

N ^o . of experiment.	s_1 in micra.	λ in ÅNGSTRÖM units.
2	7	1,5
	6	1,1
	5	0,8
	4	0,5
4	8	2,7
	(5)	(1,0)
	3	0,4
	2,5	0,25
6	8	1,7
	7	1,3
	4,5	0,5
	3	0,25
9	4	0,5
	2	0,12

If, and this is not impossible, these values of s_1 , are enlarged by photographic irradiation, the wave lengths would still become smaller. Though very desirous to be enabled to give the limits of the RÖNTGEN rays with more certainty, we think this an impossibility with the means at our disposal. Not till RÖNTGEN tubes are produced, remaining in good working condition as long as those we have made use of, but giving out rays of much greater energy, one may succeed to make measurements instead of estimations.

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